

Appendix D: Comparison with previous works

As mentioned in Sec. 4.4.1, this work is not the first to use a different background subtraction strategy from the GALEX pipeline. In Gil de Paz et al. (2007) the background is also characterized as the mean of the local background surrounding the galaxy, a strategy also adopted by Bouquin et al. (2018). In this section we make a comparison between the galaxies in Bouquin et al. (2018)'s sample and our dataset. We have 13 galaxies in common.

To make a proper comparison, in this occasion the *UV-LSB* profiles are reconstructed using the same centers, position angles, and axis ratios as in Bouquin et al. (2018), with elliptical apertures in steps of $4''$, even in those galaxies where wedge-shaped sectors were previously used. The comparison between the profiles is shown in Fig. D.1.

Since the background in both cases is characterized by the mean, the differences are related to the way the masks are constructed in the regions where the sky is estimated. The use of statistical background subtraction in our method facilitates the use of LSB-adapted detection algorithms. However, the mask construction used by Bouquin et al. (2018) is a synthesis of GALPIP masks and (FUV-NUV) based detection of unresolved foreground sources (see Bouquin et al. 2018, , Sec. 3.1). Despite the different masking, the profiles agree very well for 10 out of 13 galaxies. In general, our surface brightness profiles extend a bit further than theirs. The 3 galaxies that show important differences in the profiles are the 3 highly inclined ones NGC4307, NGC4330, and NGC5907. Interestingly, the difference in surface brightness is in the inner regions of the galaxies and not in the outer parts. This leads us to suspect that the dust lane of these objects has been treated differently between the two analyses.

Appendix E: Combination of different observing runs

In this paper, we propose a methodology for analyzing individual GALEX observing runs, using those with the longest exposure times in both bands. It should be noted, however, that some of the galaxies in the present sample have been observed in different surveys. In this section we explore the potential improvement of our methodology and the reliability of our results by integrating multiple observing runs. To this end, the data presented in Table 1 have been combined with other archival data for six galaxies in our sample. The selection of these six galaxies was made to ensure that the new data had at least 0.3 times the original exposure time in one of the two bands, and that data were available in both GALEX bands. The details of the new data are presented in Table E.1.

Table E.1. Galaxies selected for making a coadd.

Name	Survey	t_{exp} [s]		f_{exp}		$\mu_{lim}(3\sigma; 10'' \times 10'')$ [mag arcsec ⁻²]	
		FUV	NUV	FUV	NUV	FUV	NUV
NGC1042	MIS	1705	1705	0.578	0.452	29.12	29.34
NGC3368	NGS	1704	1704	0.376	0.149	29.55	29.77
NGC3486	NGS	541	1977.3	0.222	0.491	29.12	29.38
NGC4013	GII	1626.45	1626.5	0.991	0.991	29.46	29.15
NGC4321	NGS	1754.1	2932.2	0.365	0.453	29.47	29.66
NGC4330	GII/GII ^a	1689.15/1241.05	3281.15/1241.05	0.437/0.321	0.850/0.321	29.31	29.60

Notes. Galaxies are selected to have on the GALEX archive deep enough data (i.e., adding at least 30% more time) from surveys other than those used in this paper. We define $f_{exp} = \frac{t_{new}}{t_{orig}}$, where t_{new} is the exposure time of the added data and t_{orig} is the exposure time (see Table 1) of the main data used in this paper. The limiting surface brightness of the final coadd (both surveys combined) is also given.

^(a) For NGC4330 there are two more observing runs that fulfill our selection criteria. We combine both.

In order to combine the added data with the used in this paper, we have proceed as follows:

1. We apply the methodology outlined in Sec. 3.1 to each of the observing runs separately in order to obtain the background-subtracted intensity maps.
2. We combine the background-subtracted intensity maps of the added data with the original ones (the ones we called *UV LSB* in Sec. 4.4.1) using the weighted mean⁵ (Leo & Haase 1990). To measure the weights, we run `NoiseChisel` on the intensity maps, mask all the sources, and we measure the standard deviation on the masked images. The squared standard deviation values are used as proxies for the weights.
3. The methodology described in Sec. 3.2 is applied to the final coadd to subtract the effects of the PSF. To this end, we employ the models delineated in Table 2, but with the Wiener core constructed from the coadd.

The profiles of the combined data are shown in Fig. E.1, in comparison with the profiles of Sec. 4.2. The comparison of the new (combined data) profiles and the estimation of the new surface brightness limits show that the depth gained by the combined data is in most cases very small. In the FUV the maximum gain is observed in NGC4013 with $\Delta\mu_{lim} = 0.4$ mag arcsec⁻². In NUV, the maximum difference in depth is reached in NGC4330, with $\Delta\mu_{lim} = 0.45$ mag arcsec⁻². In these two galaxies, coaddition of runs with comparable exposure times (NGC4013) or multiple runs (NGC4330) results in significantly deeper surface brightness profiles.

⁵ <http://ned.ipac.caltech.edu/level5/Leo/frames.html>

Fig. D.1. Comparison between Bouquin et al. (2018) profiles and the UV-LSB profiles obtained in this work after adapting the centers, position angles and axis ratios to the values used in Bouquin et al. (2018). Rightmost panels present the difference between the surface brightness profiles in the two works ($\Delta\mu = \mu_{UVLSB} - \mu_{B18}$).

If the coaddition of multiple images does not significantly enhance the final depth, it should be used with caution. This process can introduce new sources of noise, such as the intrinsic scatter of the GALEX photometric calibration, which has an accuracy of

0.05 mag in FUV and 0.03 mag in NUV (see [Morrissey et al. 2007](#), section 4). Other light sources not present in all images (such as reflections present in the new data of NGC1042 and NGC3368), or a different position of the source in the FoV of GALEX may also contribute to the final noise. However, the results obtained for these six galaxies suggest that our methodology can still be applied when combining multiple observing runs. While this may not have a significant impact on our sample, the integration of our methodology with the weighted mean coaddition of multiple images has the potential to improve the analysis of regions with extensive data.

Fig. D.1. Cont.

Fig. D.1. Cont.

Fig. D.1. Cont.

Fig. E.1. Comparison between the surface brightness and color profiles of the galaxies using the combination of multiple GALEX runs against the profiles using a single survey (see Table E.1). See text for details.

Fig. E.1. Cont.